

Gender Role in Livestock Activities

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Abstract:- In India, most of the farm families are primarily engaged in farming and agriculture is the most primitive occupation of Indian farmers. Agricultural and livestock activities both are independently and jointly doing by male and female farmers. In some places of country animal husbandry activities are done by women. Though this study identified activities of agriculture and animal husbandry which are jointly and independently participated by male and female farmers. The study was conducted in Junagadh and Jamnagar of Saurashtra region. Total 12 villages from four talukas and two talukas from each district were selected for the study. From each selected village, 20 respondents (10 farmers and 10 farm women) were selected. Thus, total sample size was 240 respondents (120 farmers and 120 farm women). The respondents who have been engaged in agricultural activities and animal husbandry practices since last five years were purposively selected. With highest mean score (2.35) farmers had participated in field preparations activity, also secured highest rank followed by seed sowing and weeding & hoeing activities secured a second and third rank respectively. Activity like winnowing and cleaning with least mean score (1.03) secured a fifteenth rank and this activity mostly not done by farmer himself. While in case of farm women participation in agriculture, majority of women had participated in seed sowing with highest mean score (2.07) it secured first rank followed by activities like application of fertilizers and weeding & hoeing secured a second and third rank respectively. Farmers had participated in animal husbandry like selling of milk and milk product obtained a first rank with highest mean score (2.02) followed by activities of selecting a mulch animal (1.97) and getting loan & credit from the bank (1.87) secured a second and third rank, respectively. In case of women farmer in animal husbandry activity, milking of animal secured a first rank with highest mean score 2.20 followed by offering water and fodder to animal (2.13) and cleaning animal shed (2.11) secured a second and third rank respectively.

Keywords:- Gender Role, Agriculture, Livestock Activities, Farmer, Farm Women.

I. INTRODUCTION

India is an agriculture based country and livestock sector is an integral component of it and considered a key asset for rural livelihoods. It offers advantages over other agricultural sectors and is an entry point for promoting gender balance in rural areas. Women play a significant and crucial role with men in agricultural development and allied fields including in the main crop production, animal husbandry, horticulture, post-harvest operations, fisheries etc. Rural women perform various kinds of tasks on farm. Activities such as preparation of seeds for sowing, storage, dibbling and planting, irrigation, weeding and cleaning of grains, collection and storage of manures and most of the other farm operations carried out by farm women. Feeding and looking after milch cattle and bullocks are also entirely the job of farm women. Thus, they provide much of the unpaid family labour in home and on farm. Accordingly, a research on "Gender Role in Livestock activities" was conducted.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Saurashtra region. Out of 11 districts two districts viz. Junagadh and Jamnagar were selected purposively for study because Junagadh Agricultural University campus is in the Junagadh district and Jamnagar is away from the University. Two talukas from each district were selected randomly for the study. Three villages were randomly selected from each selected taluka. Thus, total 12 villages were selected for the study. From each selected village, 20 respondents (10 farmers and 10 farm women) were selected. Thus, total sample size was 240 respondents (120 farmers and 120 farm women). The respondents who have been engaged in agricultural activities and animal husbandry practices since last five years were purposively selected.

In order to collect valid and reliable data from the respondents, an interview schedule was developed according to the objectives of the study. The data were collected through personal contact using structured interview schedule. To know participation of farmers and farm women in agricultural and animal husbandry activities, the teacher made scale was used for study. Data collected for the study

were analysed using frequency, percentages and coefficient of correlation.

III. PARTICIPATION OF FARMER AND FARMWOMEN IN AGRICULTURE

Data indicated in table no.1 that with highest mean score (2.35) farmers had participated in Field preparations activity, also secured highest rank followed by seed sowing and weeding & hoeing activities secured a second and third rank respectively. While in case of farm women participation in agriculture, majority of women had

participated in seed sowing with highest mean score (2.07) it secured first rank followed by activities like application of fertilizers and weeding & hoeing secured a second and third rank respectively. In case of Farmer in agriculture, activity like Winnowing and cleaning with least mean score (1.03) secured a fifteen rank and these activities mostly not done by farmer himself. While in case of farm women, Activity like marketing of produce secured a fifteen rank with least mean score (1.03). Probable reason might be that this activity mostly had not been done by women farmer. It also concluded that in agricultural field marketing activities are performed by farmers.

Table 1 Participation in Agriculture (n=240)

Involvement of respondents in Farm Activity													
Sr. no.	Particular	Men (n=120)						Women (n=120)					
		Supervision	Actual Doing	Both	Not at all	Mean score	Rank	Supervision	Actual Doing	Both	Not at all	Mean score	Rank
1.	Manuring of field	32 (26.66)	29 (24.17)	54 (45.00)	5 (4.17)	2.10	IV	21 (17.50)	73 (60.83)	18 (15.00)	8 (6.67)	1.84	IV
2.	Ploughing of field	42 (35.00)	27 (22.50)	43 (35.83)	8 (6.67)	1.88	VII	32 (26.67)	6 (5.00)	11 (9.17)	71 (59.16)	0.64	XIV
3.	Field preparations	23 (19.17)	32 (36.67)	65 (54.16)	0 (0.00)	2.35	I	35 (29.17)	25 (20.83)	18 (15.00)	42 (35.00)	1.16	IX
4.	Seed sowing	18 (15.00)	41 (34.17)	58 (48.33)	3 (2.50)	2.28	II	18 (15.00)	52 (43.33)	42 (35.00)	8 (6.67)	2.07	I
5.	Transplanting of seedlings	36 (30.00)	32 (26.66)	26 (21.67)	26 (21.67)	1.48	X	18 (15.00)	38 (31.66)	11 (9.67)	53 (44.17)	1.06	XI
6.	Application of fertilizers	42 (35.00)	37 (30.83)	31 (25.84)	10 (8.33)	1.74	VIII	12 (10.00)	53 (44.17)	41 (34.16)	14 (11.67)	2.01	II
7.	Weeding and hoeing	25 (20.83)	18 (15.00)	69 (57.50)	8 (6.67)	2.23	III	21 (17.50)	76 (63.33)	18 (15.00)	5 (4.17)	1.89	III
8.	Application of Pesticide and Fungicides	52 (43.33)	32 (26.67)	26 (21.67)	10 (8.33)	1.62	XI	42 (35.00)	8 (6.67)	18 (15.00)	52 (43.33)	0.93	XIII
9.	Watch field/farm	64 (53.33)	12 (10.00)	28 (23.33)	16 (13.34)	1.43	XIV	45 (35.50)	32 (26.67)	11 (9.17)	32 (26.66)	1.18	VIII
10.	Irrigation	38 (31.67)	32 (26.66)	48 (40.00)	2 (1.67)	2.07	V	32 (26.66)	14 (11.67)	21 (17.50)	53 (44.17)	1.03	XII
11.	Harvesting and picking	46 (38.33)	31 (25.33)	41 (34.17)	2 (1.67)	1.93	VI	12 (10.00)	42 (35.00)	28 (23.33)	32 (26.67)	1.50	V
12.	Threshing	56 (46.66)	12 (10.00)	32 (26.67)	20 (16.67)	1.47	XII	21 (17.50)	37 (30.83)	20 (16.67)	42 (35.00)	1.29	VI
13.	Winnowing and cleaning	52 (43.33)	18 (15.00)	12 (10.00)	38 (31.67)	1.03	XV	42 (35.00)	25 (20.83)	18 (15.00)	35 (29.17)	1.22	VII
14.	Processing and storage of produce	19 (15.83)	35 (29.17)	24 (20.00)	42 (35.00)	1.34	XIII	28 (23.33)	38 (31.67)	10 (8.33)	44 (36.67)	1.12	X
15.	Marketing of produce	38 (31.67)	37 (30.83)	23 (19.17)	22 (18.33)	1.51	VIII	39 (32.50)	6 (5.00)	3 (2.50)	72 (60.00)	0.50	XV

IV. PARTICIPATION OF FARMER AND FARMWOMEN IN ANIMAL HUSBANDRY

Table 2 Participation in Animal Husbandry (n=240)

Involvement of respondents in Animal husbandry													
Sr. No.		Men (n=120)						Women (n=120)					
		Supervision	Actual Doing	Both	Not at all	Mean Score	Rank	Supervision	Actual Doing	Both	Not at all	Mean score	Rank
1.	Selecting a mulch animal	38 (31.67)	21 (17.50)	52 (43.33)	9 (7.50)	1.97	II	47 (39.16)	28 (23.33)	33 (27.50)	12 (10.00)	1.68	VII
2.	Fodder collection /cultivating	21 (17.50)	35 (29.17)	42 (35.00)	22 (18.33)	1.81	IV	52 (43.33)	32 (26.67)	22 (18.33)	14 (11.67)	1.52	VIII
3.	Cleaning animal shed	42 (35.00)	21 (17.50)	19 (15.83)	38 (31.67)	1.18	VIII	30 (25.00)	35 (29.17)	51 (42.50)	4 (3.33)	2.11	III
4.	Dung collection and cake making	56 (46.67)	8 (6.67)	11 (9.16)	45 (37.50)	0.88	IX	35 (29.17)	33 (27.50)	47 (29.16)	5 (4.17)	2.02	IV
5.	Milking of animal	52 (43.33)	16 (13.33)	21 (17.50)	31 (25.84)	1.23	VII	24 (20.00)	42 (35.00)	52 (43.44)	2 (1.67)	2.20	I
6.	Selling of milk and milk product	27 (22.50)	49 (40.83)	39 (32.50)	5 (4.17)	2.02	I	44 (36.67)	25 (20.83)	45 (37.50)	6 (5.00)	1.91	V
7.	Take care of sick animal	42 (35.00)	38 (31.67)	19 (15.83)	21 (17.50)	1.46	V	48 (40.00)	28 (23.33)	38 (31.67)	6 (5.00)	1.82	VI
8.	Offering water and fodder to animal	32 (26.67)	51 (42.50)	11 (9.16)	26 (21.67)	1.39	VI	29 (24.16)	41 (34.17)	48 (40.00)	2 (1.67)	2.13	II
9.	Getting loan and credit from the bank	22 (18.33)	44 (36.67)	38 (31.67)	16 (13.33)	1.87	III	32 (26.67)	26 (21.67)	28 (23.33)	34 (28.33)	1.40	IX

Data in a table no. 2 indicated that farmers had participated in animal husbandry like Selling of milk and milk product obtained a first rank with highest mean score (2.02) followed by activities of selecting a mulch animal (1.97) and getting loan & credit from the bank (1.87) secured a second and third rank, respectively. In case of women farmer in animal husbandry activity, milking of animal secured a first rank with highest mean score 2.20 followed by offering water and fodder to animal (2.13) and cleaning animal shed (2.11) secured a second and third rank respectively. Data in a table also concluded that majority of Animal Husbandry activities had been done by women

farmer more effectively than farmers because women farmer had been done it by herself.

V. CONCLUSION

With highest mean score (2.35) farmers had participated in Field preparations activity. Farmers are actively participating in Seed sowing and weeding & hoeing activities secured a second and third rank respectively. Activity like Winnowing and cleaning with least mean score (1.03) secured a fifteen rank and this activities mostly not done by independently farmer himself. In case of agricultural activities majority of men were participate in

activities which required muscular strengthen like field preparation. Farmers had participated in animal husbandry like Selling of milk and milk product obtained a first rank. In case of livestock activities, they were mostly done activities which were outside from their home like selection of mulch animal and getting loan.

In case of farm women participation in agriculture, majority of women had participated in seed sowing with highest mean score (2.07). Other activities like application of fertilizers and weeding & hoeing had been done by women actively. Majority of women were engaged less in activities like selling or marketing of produce because agricultural field marketing activities mostly performed by male. In case of women farmer in animal husbandry activity, milking of animal secured a first rank with highest mean score 2.20. Activity like offering water and fodder to animal and cleaning animal shed had been done by women independently. It also concluded that majority of Animal Husbandry activities had been done by women farmer more effectively than farmers because women farmer had been done it by herself. Studies also conclude that majority of women were actively participate in animal husbandry activities because of encouragement of dairy co-operatives and livestock activities doesn't brought their household activities and other responsibilities.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Anonymous. Gender and poverty in India. World Bank Country Study, Washington, D.C., USA. 1991.
- [2]. Chauhan, S.K., Gupta, M., Sharma, R.K., Rishi, M.L. and Gupta, M. An assessment of women participation in dairying. *Indian J. Dairy Sci.*, **47(2)**: 1058-1069. 1994.
- [3]. Gautam, N. and Meenakshmi. Women participation in farming of Himachal Pradesh. *Kurukshetra*, **44(6)** : 17-19. 1992.
- [4]. Jacinthe Ibrahim Rihan. "Role of Rural Women in Decision Making Regarding Livestock Management Activities: A Case Study In Elabadia Village, Damanhour District, El- Behira Governorate, Egypt.", *Fayoum Journal of Agricultural Research and Development*, 2018
- [5]. Punitha, P., Singh, S. B., & Netaji, S. R. Gender differences on training needs among farmers' discussion groups. *Indian Res. J. Ext. Edu.*, **12 (1)**: 73-77. 2012.